

REQUIREMENTS FOR A MODERN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSON

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ABSTRACT

The main goal of this article is to provide information about the use of modern methods and requirements for the teaching process in the process of the lesson and learning foreign languages.

Today, the purpose of education is not just to gain knowledge and develop skills, but also to create certain personality qualities, as well as the formation of key competencies that are especially important for the further life of a person in society. In order to make it possible to classify the knowledge, skills and abilities obtained during school, the term UEA was created – universal educational actions that allow you to plan and conduct a lesson in such a way that it corresponds to the Federal State Educational Standard. According to the standard, the requirements for the subject results of mastering a basic foreign language course should reflect:

- 1) the formation of communicative foreign language competence necessary for successful socialization and self-realization as an instrument of intercultural communication in the modern multicultural world;
- 2) knowledge of the socio-cultural specifics of the country / countries of the studied language and the ability to build their speech and non-speech behavior adequately to this specificity; the ability to distinguish common and different in the culture of the native country and the country / countries of the studied language;
- 3) achievement of a threshold level of foreign language proficiency that allows graduates to communicate orally and in writing with both native speakers of the foreign language being studied and with representatives of other countries using this language as a means of communication;
- 4) the formation of the ability to use a foreign language as a means to obtain information from foreign sources for educational and self-educational purposes.

UEA is the ability to learn, the ability of a student to successfully assimilate new knowledge independently, to form skills and competencies, including the independent organization of

this process. The ability to learn is an essential factor in improving the effectiveness of students' acquisition of subject knowledge, the formation of skills and competencies. [6]

The function of the UEA is to ensure the student's ability to independently carry out teaching activities, set educational goals, seek and use the necessary means and ways to achieve them, monitor and evaluate the process and results of activities, as well as create conditions for the harmonious development of personality and its self-realization based on readiness for continuing education; ensuring successful assimilation of knowledge, the formation of skills, skills and competencies in any subject area. Due to the change in the paradigm of education, due to the appearance of the second-generation, the requirements for the organization of a foreign language lesson have also changed. [5] A modern foreign language lesson has a number of general requirements that are characteristic of the construction of any modern lesson, as well as a number of specific features that are characteristic only of a foreign language. The document formulates both a number of general requirements for the lesson (such as the selection of means to achieve results adequate to the goals set, the formation of motivation to study the subject of a foreign language, the formation of UEA, the use of effective technologies that contribute to the effective conduct of the lesson, the specific features of the construction of a modern foreign language lesson) and a more detailed list of them. [1]

To conduct a lesson according to the new system, the teacher must:

- clearly formulate its goals, determine its optimal content in accordance with the requirements of the curriculum and the objectives of the lesson, taking into account the level of training and preparedness of students;
- to predict the level of students' assimilation of scientific knowledge, the formation of skills and abilities, both in the lesson and at its individual stages;
- choose the most rational methods, techniques and means of teaching, stimulating and controlling and their optimal impact at each stage of the lesson;
- choose the optimal combination of different forms of work in the classroom and stimulate maximum independence of students in the learning process, providing cognitive activity;
- the lesson should be problematic and developing, the teacher should aim at cooperation with students and be able to direct their cooperation with themselves and classmates;
- the teacher also needs to organize problematic and search situations, activate the activities of students and create conditions for a successful learning process by students. [4]

At different levels of secondary school, a foreign language lesson has its own characteristics. Chapter 2 of this thesis will describe the features of conducting a lesson on the PC model for secondary school. At the middle stage of education, the educational and developmental value of the subject increases, the goals of teaching oral communication and reading to oneself are balanced, awareness of learning a foreign language increases, the role of independent work increases, the content of texts for reading and listening and speech of students becomes more complicated, the systematization of grammatical phenomena begins. In modern realities, the teacher needs to effectively spend the lesson time in order to form students' skills to work with new material, which increases quantitatively and qualitatively becomes more complicated every year. [2] Special attention needs to be paid to the formation of

independent work skills, which is facilitated by the PC model. The recently appeared educational model “Flipped Classroom” is gradually gaining popularity among teachers who want to change the traditional approach to learning. The PC model differs significantly from the traditional teaching system. The emphasis in it is on encouraging students to self-study, while the role of the teacher is changed from active to passive, from the role of a “talking head” to the role of a facilitator, which translates the emphasis towards individualization of education, since in these conditions the teacher will be able to pay attention to each student. However, the introduction of the PC model does not reduce, but on the contrary, increases the amount of work for the teacher. Since changing the teaching model is difficult in it and requires increased attention, time and effort on the part of the teacher, including preparing the material for each lesson and determining its optimal content in accordance with the objectives of the lesson. It can be assumed that over time, working on the new system will become a habit and it will seem easier if you develop your own teaching algorithm and have a large baggage of methodological developments.[3]

The PC model has both a number of significant advantages and disadvantages. However, with the competent introduction of this model into use in the classroom, the value of these shortcomings will not be so high, in contrast to the results obtained. One of the advantages of PC model training is the ability to implement the requirements of the standard to a greater extent than training on the traditional model allows. Teaching according to the PC model also requires the teacher to clearly set goals and determine the optimal content of the lesson, taking into account the level of training of students; requires forecasting the level of assimilation of knowledge by students.

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